

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

A broader tumor suppressor-like function for NLR genes.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Nucleotide synthesis regulation by NLRP7 (together with NLRP/NOD2 control of p53 and regulation of p53 family gene p63) control of Rb1-associated E2Fs, and regulation of genes required for cell cycle progression including *TPX2*, *ASPM*, *NUSAP* indicated a tumor suppressor-like function for NLR genes. NLR regulation of senescence program actors through interferon pathway regulation suggests that NLR genes execute complex cell-intrinsic and cell-extrinsic regulation of transformation in humans.